

WinWin 4 WorkLife

D8.2 General EC Policy Briefs

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Executive summary

The *WinWin4WorkLife (WW4WL)* project addresses the transformative impact of remote work (RWA) across Europe, with a focus on its social, economic, and spatial dimensions. While initially seen as a win-win for productivity, work-life balance, and environmental sustainability, the rapid adoption of remote work—especially during and after the COVID-19 pandemic—has revealed complex challenges and inequalities. This policy brief outlines how WW4WL responds to these issues and provides a foundation for evidence-based policy development at EU and Member State levels. This policy brief is based on the lexicon about remote work (D2.1) and an extensive literature review (D2.2).

Key Policy Issues and Challenges Remote work affects diverse policy areas, including mental health, gender equality, spatial segregation, digital skills, and urban-rural dynamics. Despite its benefits, it risks exacerbating socio-spatial inequalities, reinforcing gender roles, increasing digital divides, and shifting pressures onto suburban and rural infrastructures. Legal inconsistencies, particularly concerning taxation and social security across borders, further complicate the landscape.

WW4WL's Interdisciplinary and Comparative Approach To address these gaps, WW4WL undertakes a multi-country, mixed-method research design across five European countries (DE, FI, LU, PT, SK), including:

- A systematic literature review and typology of RWA (working from home, somewhere, or anywhere)
- Large-scale surveys of employers and employees
- A dedicated digital nomad survey
- Qualitative studies including time-use diaries and in-depth interviews
- Spatial and transport modelling to forecast spatial and environmental impacts
- Stakeholder engagement through panels and workshops to co-develop practical solutions

This unique design allows the project to explore both the *employee and employer perspectives* while connecting working and living conditions, and to incorporate cultural and institutional variations across the EU.

Policy Contributions WW4WL provides early insights into how remote work can:

- Improve productivity and mental health
- Support rural revitalization and urban adaptation
- Help address skills shortages and labour gaps
- Contribute to EU climate goals and smart city missions

It also highlights policy blind spots, including the need for harmonized social security rules, stronger mental health protections, and inclusive infrastructure investment.

Recommendations Preliminary recommendations include:

- Strengthening EU directives on the right to disconnect and mental health in the workplace
- Promoting equitable access to remote work through digital infrastructure and skills training
- Addressing gender inequalities and housing market pressures through targeted regulation
- Integrating remote work into national climate and spatial strategies to avoid rebound effects

Next Steps The project will produce empirical analyses and develop forecasting tools for remote work uptake and its spatial consequences. A second phase will translate findings into actionable policy options through co-creation workshops, tailored to specific regional and cross-border contexts.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Description
DE	Germany
EC	European Commission
ETUC	European Trade Union Confederation
HE	Horizon Europe
FI	Finland
LU	Luxembourg
PT	Portugal
RWA	Remote Working Arrangements
SK	Slovakia
WFA	Working from anywhere
WFH	Working from home
WFS	Working from somewhere
WW4WL	WinWin4WorkLife

1. Introduction

Remote work is reshaping the European labour market, with wide-ranging **social, economic, and spatial impacts**. The **WinWin4WorkLife (WW4WL) project** aims to explore these impacts supporting evidence-based policymaking.

1.1. Policy issues related to remote work

While remote work exists for decades, the COVID-19 pandemic greatly accelerated its adoption (Milasi et al., 2020). Initially, it was seen as a win-win: offering better work-life balance for employees, broader talent pools to recruit from for employers, reduced congestion and transport-related emissions in urban areas, and increased attractiveness of rural areas which could help in reversing an ageing and shrinking population in these areas. However, the discourse around remote work has changed and concerns are growing about its social, economic, and spatial impacts (Countouris et al., 2023). For employees, blurred boundaries between work and private life can harm mental well-being, leading to burnout. Employers face challenges maintaining productivity, creativity, and team cohesion, prompting some to rethink the value of office presence. Remote work may also reshape cities and rural areas in unintended ways. Commuting savings can be offset by increased non-work travel or relocation of households and businesses to suburban and rural areas lacking adequate infrastructure. Moreover, social and spatial inequalities risk deepening: women with children may face reinforced gender roles, digital divides may widen, and remote workers who decide to relocate can drive up housing prices leading to problems of segregation and gentrification. Cross-border regions and international mobility of digital nomads add complexity, where the uptake of remote work is influenced by differences in taxation and social security across countries.

Therefore, key policy concerns include remote work's impact on:

- Social aspects: work-life balance; mental health and well-being
- Economic aspects: productivity, creativity, and innovation; access to labour markets; future trends in remote work across different sectors, company sizes, and locations
- Spatial impacts: changes in mobility and transport-related emissions; urban-rural dynamics
- Socio-spatial inequalities: gender roles; digital skills divide; segregation and gentrification

A good understanding of these remote work's impacts is imperative as EU countries seek to foster inclusive and sustainable growth by ensuring that more employees, employers, and communities benefit from remote work, while simultaneously reducing populations at risk of exclusion and mitigating negative spatial and environmental impacts.

1.2. Policy and research challenges and how the WW4WL project deals with them

However, there are significant challenges in obtaining a good understanding of remote work. These include:

- Knowledge is scattered between disciplines and sectors. As remote work affects the economy, society, and spaces, we urgently need an **interdisciplinary understanding** based on insights from economics, sociology, public health, psychology, geography, spatial and transport planning, and law. The WW4WL project has therefore done a systematic literature review, resulting in a lexicon on remote work and an in-depth overview of the state-of-the-art. We also need better insights into the needs and expectations not only from employees and employers but also stakeholders in policy and practice. WW4WL is therefore building a Stakeholder Panel, which will soon be consulted via an online Delphi survey and later onwards invited for a series of workshops.
- There is a pressing need for **robust empirical data** from employees and employers **allowing comparative research** on remote work across cultures, borders, and welfare systems. WW4WL has therefore started a large-scale data collection in five different European countries (DE, FI, LU, PT, SK), involving both employers and employees. In doing so, unique datasets will be built offering insights in social, economic, and spatial impacts from a variety of urban, rural, and cross-border areas.
- Remote work brings the professional work sphere closer to the private life sphere. This means identifying **working conditions and living conditions** essential for a healthy, inclusive, and sustainable implementation of remote work. As WW4WL collects data from employers and employees, we will be able to confront working conditions with living conditions.
- There is a lack of **tools to estimate, forecast, and visualize** the spatial and environmental impacts of remote work. WW4WL will therefore develop different types of spatial models (i.e., agent-based models and 4-step transport models).

To overcome these challenges, the WW4WL consortium is highly interdisciplinary which guarantees a holistic study of remote work and its impacts. WW4WL is, therefore, one of very few projects that addresses and reconciles important dichotomies inherent to remote work, such as: employer vs. employee perspectives; living vs. working conditions; regional/national vs. cross-border/international remote work; urban vs. rural settings. Once the data collection is finished, WW4WL will perform *joint* analyses of living and working conditions, accounting for the interactions between the private and work spheres, in order to determine their relative role on, for example, mental health, skills divide, and inequalities. This approach contrasts with most of literature, which tends to be narrowly focused on one or few factors without considering their interactions and wider implications. Moreover, by collecting data in five different countries, WW4WL will be able to account for the role of cultural and institutional factors as well as policy settings of national housing and labour markets in mediating the effects of remote work.

This contrasts with many single-country studies, which are not able to capture the role of such mediating factors.

By addressing the above challenges, WW4WL will help to evaluate the effectiveness of current labour laws, tax policies, and social security systems. This will provide useful information for social partners representing employees (European Trade Union Confederation – ETUC) and employers (BusinessEurope representing private firms, SMEUnited representing small businesses, SGI Europe representing public employers; Eurochambres representing chambers of commerce and industry) to strengthen their role in shaping labour markets, employment, and social policies.

The WW4WL project is one of the first Horizon Europe projects that will provide novel findings on the impact of remote work on angles critical for employees and employers: (1) work-life balance and loneliness; (2) mental, physical health, and productivity; (3) skills divide of specific groups (gender, rural/urban; residents/cross-border workers); (4) enabling conditions, both in terms of practical working conditions and corporate culture. Moreover, WW4WL also considers the implications of remote work for urban and rural areas: (i) how it could result in less congestion and transport-related emissions in urban areas without harming urban vitality, and (ii) how it could prevent brain drain for rural areas without creating problems of segregation and gentrification. In doing so, WW4WL will provide new insights that are relevant for different **priorities of the European Commission** as well as Horizon Europe’s [mission on climate adaptation and smart cities](#) (see Table 1).

Table 1: WW4WL contributions to EC priorities and HE missions

EC priorities	The WW4WL surveys, models and workshops will help to ...
<p>A new plan for Europe's sustainable prosperity and competitiveness</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Objective: Boosting productivity with digital tech diffusion - Objective: Tackling the skills and labour gaps 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify types of organizational support needed from employers to ensure productivity, creativity, and innovation among remote workers - Understand how remote work could help to prevent brain drain in rural areas by attracting new residents but also keeping the local community and guaranteeing their "right to stay" - Identify how remote work is linked to the development of digital skills of employees - Understand if remote work is really a solution for employers dealing with skill shortage in recruitments (in case of a small local pool of talents) and staff retention
<p>Supporting people, strengthening our societies and our social model</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Objective: Deliver opportunities, stability, and wellbeing for everyone - Objective: Tackle inequality, regional disparities and discrimination 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify the conditions needed so that remote work does not lead to unfair wages (e.g., for mothers with children), problems with work-life balance and mental wellbeing, or disparities in cross-border regions so that "nobody is left behind" - Identify the conditions needed so that remote work does not lead to unintended mobility effects, segregation or gentrification so that "no place is left behind" - Understand how remote work could prevent brain drain for rural areas and revert demographic changes of an ageing and shrinking population in these areas
HE mission Climate Adaptation and Smart Cities	The WW4WL surveys, models and workshops will help to ...
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop urban environments at the forefront of sustainability and innovation - 100 climate-neutral and smart European cities by 2030 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify the conditions needed so that remote work leads to a reduction in congestion and transport-related emissions

2. Evidence and analysis

This policy brief draws on findings of two deliverables of the WW4WL project. These are:

- D2.1 *Lexicon on remote work*
- D2.2 *Report on state-of-the-art, research gaps and conceptual diagram*

2.1. A typology of remote work

Remote work refers to flexible work arrangements regarding place and time of working. Remote workers perform at least part of their working time outside the traditional office, using digital tools and ICT to stay connected with their employer (Shirmohammadi et al., 2022; Spreitzer et al., 2017), thus eliminating the need to commute to work on a daily basis.

Remote work has been a recognized for decades. It began in the 1970s, when the development of ICT made it possible to connect city headquarters to their satellite offices in more distant locations. By the late 1990s, personal computers and the Internet enabled working from home. Today, wireless Internet and public WiFi allow employees to work from anywhere, leading to a variety of remote work arrangements (RWA). However, the absence of universal accepted definitions create inconsistencies in our understanding of social, economic, and spatial impacts of remote work. The WW4WL project, therefore, proposes a typology based on the **location dependency and flexibility**, distinguishing between three main types of RWA (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Typology of remote work

- **Working from home (WFH):** location-dependent work tied to the residence. Synonyms are “home-based work” or “working from the home office”. Employees can work from home full-time, but there is now a trend towards “hybrid work” where employees alternate between home and office. Employees can also decide to work from home only part of the working day and then go to the office for the rest of the day. This is known as “flexible work”, which provides more time flexibility than the typical 9-to-5 working schedule.
- **Working from somewhere (WFS):** location-dependent work but tied to a third place other than the residence or the conventional office. Examples are satellite offices and co-working spaces. These are clearly designed for productivity with professional office amenities.
- **Working from anywhere (WFA):** highly flexible work not tied to a specific location. Digital nomads are an extreme case with no fixed workplace base, working remotely from almost any place at any time. Workations are a less extreme case. Employees still have a fixed workplace base, combining it with the same flexibility as a digital nomad in a vacation setting but only on a temporary basis. Mobile work is another less extreme case of WFA. Employees combine their fixed workplace base with work at third places that are not necessarily designed for productivity (e.g., public places such as cafés, libraries). In order to recreate the capabilities of a traditional office, tools and technologies such as laptops, mobile phones, cloud-based applications and VPN for secure access to networks are needed. The concept therefore underscores the importance of connectivity and mobility in modern work.

2.2. State of the art on remote work

Knowledge about various forms of remote work has been growing since the 2000s and surged during the COVID-19 pandemic. A Scopus database search from 1970 to 2024 found nearly 30.000 articles on remote work, with 50% published since 2020. The WW4WL project has systematically reviewed this extensive body of literature.

Because remote work blends private and work life, WW4WL has reviewed the literature from both **employee and employer perspectives** to identify key **benefits**, enabling **conditions** but also **challenges** for a healthy, inclusive, and sustainable implementation of remote work. By combining these two perspectives (employee and employer) and studying social impacts together with economic and spatial impacts, WW4WL is one of the few projects that strives for a holistic understanding of RWA.

2.2.1. Remote work from an employee's perspective

Key benefits of remote work for employees are:

- **Improved work-life balance and mental health:** Remote work allows for flexible scheduling, more efficient rest periods, decreased time in meetings and commuting, and better time management, which can decrease work-life conflicts (Asgari et al., 2023; Rubin et al., 2020). It can reduce stress (Freire & Alves, 2023) and improve mental health, job satisfaction, and overall happiness (Gueguen & Senik, 2023).
- **Higher productivity:** Remote work can improve productivity due to fewer distractions, greater autonomy and feelings of trust, better digital and decision-making skills, and even the “Hawthorne effect” where awareness of being observed (whether or not that is correct) boosts performance (Angelici & Profeta, 2023; Barrero et al., 2021; Brucks & Levav, 2022; Deole et al., 2023; Kim et al. 2021; Martin et al., 2022a).
- **Reduced commuting burden:** Remote work reduces the need to commute on a daily basis. It can save time and costs, lower emissions, and reduce health risks from being exposed to air pollution, noise, and traffic (Beck & Hensher, 2021; Shortall et al., 2022).
- **More residential freedom:** Remote workers no longer need to live within an acceptable commuting distance from their employer. They have more flexibility to live in locations that match their lifestyle preferences – whether in suburban or rural areas that typically offer more space at an affordable price, in urban areas with easy access to a variety of amenities (de Abreu e Silva; Mouratidis et al., 2021), or even abroad taking advantage of geoarbitrage by relocating to lower-cost regions while earning wages from wealthier regions (Holleran, 2022).

But these positive impacts can only be achieved under certain conditions:

- **Suitable remote work environment:** Having a quiet and well-equipped remote workspace (de Abreu e Silva, 2022) with limited distractions, shared household

duties, and strong digital support is essential in maintaining productivity and well-being.

- **Organizational support:** Employers need to support their remote workers by setting clear objectives and expectations, using an effective communication style, maintaining a culture of trust, and providing the necessary (digital) resources and support that help their workforce to manage workloads effectively (Bertoni et al., 2021; Gueguen & Senik, 2023; Lundqvist et al., 2022; Pelly et al., 2022; Vander Elst et al., 2017).
- **Reliable infrastructure:** Adequate broadband, public transport, and services in suburban and rural areas are essential for sustaining remote work viability (de Abreu e Silva, 2022).

Remote work also poses challenges to remote workers:

- **Work-life conflicts and burnouts:** Remote work can lead to increased digital monitoring, information overload, and the continued use of ICTs during leisure time, blurring boundaries between work and private life (Antón et al., 2023; Braithwaite et al., 2023; Brucks & Levav, 2022; Martin et al., 2022a, b). The higher flexibility could also shift working hours towards “non-standard” hours (Giménez-Nadal et al. 2020; Pabilonia & Vernon, 2022), creating difficulties to “unplug” and causing concentration problems, stress, mental exhaustion, and burnout (Consiglio et al., 2023; Niebuhr et al., 2022). To prevent burnout, employers should offer flexible scheduling, and encourage their employees to take breaks and set boundaries to their work hours (Asgari et al., 2023). Technostress appears to be a key factor related to burnout (Consiglio et al., 2023), showing the importance of providing training, resources and tools for stress management and mental health support. Additionally, without proper ergonomic remote work office setups, physical discomfort and strain can further contribute to mental health issues (Seinsche et al., 2023). Employers should therefore also invest in their employees’ health by investing in good-quality remote workspaces.
- **Gender inequality:** Women, particularly with young children, often choose remote work to balance responsibilities. They sometimes even accept a wage penalty to be able to work remotely. However, this reaffirms gender roles and inequalities (Derndorfer et al., 2021; Giménez-Nadal & Velilla, 2024; Pabilonia & Vernon, 2022; Restrepo & Zeballos, 2020; van Tienoven et al., 2023).
- **Isolation and reduced career visibility:** Remote workers may feel isolated, lonely, and disconnected due to a lack of in-person interactions with colleagues (Loezar-Hernández et al., 2023; O’Hare et al., 2024; Schade et al., 2021). It may also limit networking opportunities and career growth. Employers should therefore facilitate virtual engagement and set-up mentorship programs (Aidla et al., 2023; Pataki-Bittó & Kun, 2022).
- **Digital skills divide:** Employees with lower digital literacy may struggle with remote work. While the pandemic narrowed the gap in digital skills across age and gender, it widened the gap between lower and higher educated (Hauret et al., 2024), potentially contributing to increasing income inequalities. Employers

should invest in digital training programs, provide user-friendly tools, and offer IT support to ensure all employees (no matter if they work remotely or on-site) can work effectively (Martin et al., 2022a).

- **Shifts in daily and residential mobility:** The time saved for commuting is often spent on other non-work-related travel, potentially affecting traffic patterns, transportation mode choices, and travel distances (Mouratidis et al., 2021; Ravalet & Rérat, 2019; Staves et al., 2023). The impact of this rebound effect will depend on where remote workers live. Some may move to suburban or rural areas for more space, being close to nature and affordability, while others may remain in cities because they also value having amenities nearby (de Abreu e Silva & Melo, 2018; Mouratidis et al., 2021). An increase in non-work-related travel in suburban and rural areas is often related to more car use and more transport-related emissions. However, this is not necessarily the case for remote workers in urban areas. A lot depends on whether remote workers could have easy access to non-work related amenities. Spatial planning must therefore adapt to shifting work patterns by developing “15-minute neighbourhoods” (be it in urban, suburban, or even rural areas) with accessible workplaces, services, and recreational spaces (Allam et al., 2022).
- **Housing market pressure:** Increased demand for housing in desirable remote work locations can drive up real estate prices and displace lower-income residents. This is also the case in places popular with digital nomads (Biagetti et al., 2024). To avoid problems of socio-spatial segregation and gentrification, policymakers should regulate housing markets to prevent displacement.

2.2.2. Remote work from an employer’s perspective

Key benefits of remote work for employers are:

- **Higher productivity and creativity:** Some studies show no significant differences in productivity between remote work and office-based work (Beck & Hensher, 2021). Creativity might be a bit lower in terms of less ideas, but the ideas generated are often of higher quality (Brucks & Levav, 2022).
- **Bargaining power:** If employees value remote work highly, they might accept lower wages in exchange, leading to a wage penalty (Glass & Noonan, 2016). However, there exists ambiguity about this. Remote work could also lead to a wage premium because of the increase in productivity (Arntz et al., 2022).
- **Cost savings:** Remote work can reduce real estate costs for employers by downsizing office spaces or adopting a hub-and-spoke model maintaining a smaller central office in a major city and satellite offices in cheaper suburban or regional locations closer to where employees live (Asgari et al., 2023). Remote work could also lower expenses related to business-travel and overhead costs such as heating and electricity.
- **Access to talent:** Remote work may enable employers to tap into a broader pool of talent and recruit skilled employees globally (Davis et al., 2022; Macaluso & Waddell, 2022; Soroui, 2021). This is especially relevant for companies seeking specific skills that are not readily available in their local area. Remote work not only

grants access to talent, but could also lower salary costs due to regional differences in living expenses (Brucks & Levav, 2022).

- **Retention of staff:** Remote work can help to increase job satisfaction and to retain highly valued employees whose skills would be difficult to replace within the company (Soroui, 2021; Šmite & Moe, 2024)
- **More distributed economic activity:** Businesses in suburban or rural areas may benefit from increased local spending as employees work closer to home, revitalizing local economies (Beck & Hensher, 2021).

However, conditions for success are:

- **Management style:** In order to obtain productivity and creativity benefits, employers should adjust their leadership strategies and organizational support policies (Kagerl & Starzetz, 2023; Stoker et al., 2022). It requires a cultural shift towards trust, while also valuing autonomy, flexibility, and output over mere office presence (Allen et al., 2024; Angelici & Profeta, 2023; Korkeakunnas et al., 2023).
- **Continuous training:** Technological adaptation plays a vital role in the success of remote work. Proficiency in digital tools is crucial for remote workers. Employers should therefore continue investing in technological training and support (Aggarwal et al., 2023; Allen et al., 2024; Boutros et al, 2023; Martin et al., 2022a)
- **Strong ICT infrastructure:** Companies with strong digital infrastructures tend to see more positive impacts of remote work (Allen et al., 2024; Błaszczuk et al., 2022; Fontaneda et al., 2023; Kitagawa et al., 2021; Patanjali & Bhatta, 2022).
- **Compensation adjustments:** In order to benefit from a larger pool of talent and attract top talent, companies may need to offset the employee's costs related to remote work (e.g., Internet, heating) by offering this person a "telework package" or a wage premium (Biea et al., 2024).

Employers also face challenges:

- **Team cohesion and company culture:** To maintain engagement of its remote workers, employers should invest in virtual team-building activities and clear communication strategies. They could also consider adapted workplace strategies that balance office downsizing with decentralized satellite offices. Such satellite offices are usually located closer to where employees live. This helps the employee to save commuting time and costs, with a positive effect on well-being, while at the same time maintaining collaborations with colleagues and team cohesion.
- **Managing remote teams:** Remote workers might work in different time zones, regions and cultures, which may complicate management of logistics. Flexible scheduling and localized management approaches can help address these issues.
- **Economic disruptions in urban area:** Declining demand for office space in urban areas because of remote work can affect local businesses. Cities should therefore explore mixed-use developments to revitalize urban centres.

3. Policy implications and policy recommendations

The WW4WL project aims to create a healthy, inclusive, and sustainable future for remote work. We therefore reviewed remote work policies across the EU and all EU member states from these three perspectives. Together with insights from our literature review, we can already formulate some preliminary policy implications, but these need to be further elaborated in the course of the project.

A review of remote work policies across all EU member states reveals a clear trend: most countries have updated their labour laws to include provisions for remote work, largely in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. These policies primarily focus on administrative and legal frameworks, such as eligibility criteria, employer obligations, and formal agreements. However, **mental health, inclusion, and sustainability are rarely addressed explicitly**, despite growing concerns over the psychological impacts of remote work (e.g., isolation, stress, and burnout), gender inequalities and a digital skills divide, and rebound effects in mobility and urban-rural dynamics.

Before we make concrete policy recommendations about remote work and health, inclusion, and sustainability, we must stress that everything depends on what happens in terms of **taxation and social security**. Current international (OECD Model for tax purposes) and European regulations (Reg. 883/2004 for social security purposes) are not designed for remote work. As both regulatory frameworks date back for some years ago, they are not equipped to the new forms of work. This could result in financial repercussions and limit the uptake of remote work, especially for cross-border workers. These frameworks urgently need to be revised taken into account the different types of remote work from Figure 1.

3.1. Remote work and health

Several studies have shown how a good work-life balance is necessary for mental health. In this context, three EU directives can be of particular relevance for remote workers: the **Working Time Directive** (Directive 2003/88/EC), the **Transparent and Predictable Working Conditions Directive** (Directive (EU) 2019/1152), and the **Work-Life Balance Directive** (Directive (EU) 2019/1158). It might be necessary to revise those regulations in the light of the widespread adoption of remote work.

Another important EU directive is the **Right to Disconnect** (e.g. Directive (EU) 2019/1158; Directive 2003/88/EC), which has been adopted by several countries (e.g. France, Belgium, Spain). While not always framed as a mental health measure, it plays a crucial role in reducing work-related stress by allowing employees to disengage outside of working hours.

Policy recommendations include:

- **Expand the mental health focus in labour regulations:**
 - o Integrate mental health promotion as a core component of national and EU-level remote work policies.
 - o Pathway: (i) Amend national labour codes to include mandatory mental health risk assessments for remote workers, (ii) Promote employer guidelines on social connectedness, workload management, and access to mental health support, (iii) Link these changes to existing EU frameworks such as the European Pillar of Social Rights.
- **Strengthen and harmonize the right to disconnect across member states:**
 - o Expand the right to disconnect with clear implementation rules and tie it explicitly to mental health objectives.
 - o Pathway: (i) Create an EU-level directive with minimum standards, including education campaigns and enforcement mechanisms, (ii) Support national monitoring bodies to ensure compliance, with tools for workers to report violations.
- **Support psychosocial well-being through workplace design:**
 - o Encourage hybrid work models that promote both flexibility and social interaction.
 - o Pathway: (i) Incentivize satellite offices or co-working spaces that offer shared, local spaces for remote workers, (ii) Develop urban and regional planning guidelines to foster inclusive, connected communities for both remote and on-site workers.
- **Build a common data and monitoring framework:**
 - o Develop EU-wide key performance indicators (KPIs) on the mental health impacts of remote work.
 - o Pathway: (i) Fund collaborative research and data collection through Eurofound or the European Agency for Safety & Health at Work (EU-OSHA), (ii) Mandate annual reporting on remote work outcomes at both national and EU levels.

3.2. Remote work and inclusion

While current policy frameworks rarely address the inclusion impacts of remote work, literature reveals several pathways through which remote work can reduce or—if poorly managed—increase socio-spatial inequalities. Tackling inequalities, regional disparities, and possible discriminations when it comes to remote work, requires an integral and cross-sectoral approach, with adequate coordination between policies within different directorates and Commissioner's responsibilities. Policy recommendations therefore include:

- **Bilateral regulations on RWA:**
 - o Harmonize existing regulations, especially relevant in the context of cross-border labour markets.
 - o Pathway: (i) Amend bilateral agreements on fiscal issues due to RWA expanding the European framework agreement on the application of Article 16(1) of Regulation (EC) No. 883/2004 in cases of habitual cross-border telework.
- **Invest in digital infrastructure so that no place is left behind**
 - o Invest in digital infrastructure in underserved regions and sectors (e.g., rural areas, public services).
 - o Pathway: (i) Use EU structural and investment funds to expand broadband and digital access, (ii) Create regional telework hubs with shared facilities and training resources.
- **Bridge the digital skills gap**
 - o Provide digital skills training for vulnerable groups (low-skilled, unemployed, older adults).
 - o Pathways: (i) Expand Erasmus+ and European Social Fund+ programmes to include remote work-specific upskilling, (ii) Encourage employer-led training with public co-financing.
- **Address gender inequality**
 - o Monitor and regulate wage disparities linked to remote work
 - o Pathway: (i) Mandate gender-disaggregated reporting of remote work uptake and pay levels, (ii) Incentivize companies to offer flexible work options equitably across genders.
- **Create a common EU framework on telework equity**
 - o Develop EU-wide indicators to monitor teleworkability and inclusion.
 - o Pathway: (i) Establish a European Remote Work Observatory, (ii) Harmonize labour statistics (e.g., remote work uptake by region, sector, and demographic).

3.3. Remote work and sustainability

While current policy frameworks rarely address the sustainability impacts of remote work, literature reveals several pathways through which remote work can reduce or—if poorly managed—increase environmental footprints. Drawing on this evidence, we propose the following policy recommendations:

- **Promote sustainable commuting and avoid rebound effects**
 - o Incentivize hybrid work arrangements that maintain proximity to urban centres and public transport to avoid residential sprawl.
 - o Pathway: (i) Urban planning incentives to maintain high-density housing with access to public transport, (ii) Tax credits for employers who support “remote-first but city-connected” models, (iii) Invest in cycling and public transport infrastructure to complement hybrid work models.

- **Align remote work policies with broader climate goals**
 - Integrate remote work considerations into national climate strategies, transport planning, and urban development policies.
 - Pathway: (i) Require environmental impact assessments of large-scale remote work policies, (ii) Include telework as a variable in climate action plans and emission modelling, (iii) Facilitate data-sharing between transport, housing, and labour ministries to track the evolving impacts of remote work.

4. Knowledge gaps and next steps

Our knowledge about the impact of remote work relies on insights from pre COVID-19 pandemic period, and most importantly during the lockdowns. Therefore, most of these studies were conducted in a general context of uncertainty due to a global health crisis. Since then, the practice of RWA has evolved in both its intensity—regarding the occupations concerned and its frequency— and the friendliness degrees of companies managerial practices. There is now need for post-COVID research to differentiate between COVID-19 specific impacts and general remote work effects in order to understand the long-term impacts. Moreover, most studies focused on WFH, neglecting other forms of remote work (WFS, WFA), and are usually country-specific. WW4WL, on the other hand, distinguishes between different types of RWA and uses a multi-country approach. This allows us to explore the role of institutional and cultural contexts in the offer by employers and use by employees of RWA. Furthermore, differences between gender, age, and location will provide granular evidence-based policy recommendations.

While we have already accumulated a fair amount of knowledge on some topics (e.g., work-life balance, mental health, productivity, mobility), others remain understudied (see Table 2).

Table 2: Knowledge gaps in the state-of-the-art literature on RWA

Social impacts	Mental health and well-being	Lack of employer perspective
		Insufficient attention to the influence of job roles and hierarchical levels in the organization
		Need for more qualitative research
	Work-life balance and quality of time	Limited comparative analyses across types of RWA in terms of time use and multitasking
		Gaps in understanding the role of family, finances, housing conditions, and domestic-professional conflicts
		Potential for full-time RWA to replace part-time work needs further study
Underexplored inequalities in time-use quality and gender disparities		
Economic impacts	Uptake of RWA by employers and employees	Scarce studies differentiating between the willingness and ability to adopt RWA, both for employees and employers
		Underexplored employer attitudes toward RWA
	Organization support and productivity	Narrow focus on isolated managerial practices rather than holistic organizational strategies
		Need for firm-level and longitudinal studies on productivity and burnout over time
	Digital skills	Lack of clarity on how different digital skills are affected by RWA and how up-skilling is supported
	Recruitment and skills shortages	Limited evidence on strategic use of RWA by employers to combat local labour shortages
		Post-COVID wage effects are poorly understood, particularly regarding WFH vs WFA
	Wages and inequality	Insufficient exploration of inequality beyond gender (e.g., ethnicity, socio-economic status)
Cross-border issues		Complex legal implications for taxation and social security in cross-border RWA are under-researched
	Insufficient data on cross-border remote workers	
Spatial impacts	Activity and travel behaviour	Lack of employer perspective
		Need for more qualitative research capturing subjective experiences
		Need for standardized, multi-day data collection
		Little research is comparing physical activity levels of remote and office workers
	Transport-related emissions	Rebound effects on mobility are often omitted
		Lack of longitudinal; real-world studies on changes in emissions due to RWA
	Residential location decisions by employees	Unclear causality between remote work and residential decisions
		Few studies compare remote work's importance versus other housing factors
		Few studies about RWA and multi-locality living (except in Nordic countries)
	Workplace location decisions by employees	Unclear impact on rural revitalization, spatial inequality, and long-term migration trends between urban and rural areas
		Unstudied: whether RWA allows employees to consider jobs beyond traditional commuting distance
	Company location decisions by employers	Focus is mostly on downsizing, not full relocation due to RWA
	Socio-spatial inequality	Minimal understanding of RWA's role in urban segregation and demographic shifts
		Digital nomadism
Need for larger survey samples and more longitudinal research		

To address these knowledge gaps, the WW4WL project is implementing a comprehensive research strategy involving both employers and employees across 5 European countries (DE, FI, LU, PT, SK) with different cultures and welfare systems. The upcoming phases include:

1. **Employer Survey:** A large-scale survey targeting companies with at least five employees is underway to gather data on remote work policies, workforce productivity, and mental health concerns. In doing so, WW4WL is one of the few projects that explicitly takes the employer perspective into account.
2. **Employee Study:** Concurrently, an extensive employee study is being conducted to delve into individual experiences with different types of RWA. This study comprises three sequential components: (i) online questionnaire, (ii) time use diaries for one day working remotely and another day working at the office with GPS tracking over a longer period, and (iii) in-depth interviews. In doing so, WW4WL will combine quantitative and qualitative research on RWA experiences of employees.
3. **Digital Nomad Survey:** In addition to the employer and employee survey, a specific survey for digital nomads is conducted in Portugal. This survey delves deeper into the reasons why digital nomads prefer Portugal, and specifically Lisbon, where they live/work in the city and how they ‘use’ different neighbourhoods in the city. This information will provide insights into segregation and gentrification caused by digital nomads.
4. **Empirical analyses and forecasting models:** The collected data will be analyzed to identify living and working conditions for a healthy, inclusive, and sustainable implementation of remote work in urban, rural, and cross-border areas. Data will also be used as input for models forecasting trends in the uptake of remote work, as well as mobility and land use patterns. These forecasting models offers also new visualization tools for the spatial impacts of RWA. Special attention will be given to the uptake of remote work in a cross-border area like Luxembourg with a dedicated model simulating the impact of cross-border tax-benefit rules.
5. **Stakeholder Engagement:** Insights from the employer and employee studies will inform a series of local co-creation workshops. These sessions will bring together stakeholders—including experts, policymakers, and practitioners—to deliberate on sustainable solutions and the future of remote work in specific regions. These local workshops will address some very specific spatial ambiguities of RWA such as under what conditions it can be a solution to brain drain in rural areas or how it can be a solution to cope with an expensive housing market in urban areas without stimulating further suburbanization.

This structured approach aims to generate robust, evidence-based policy recommendations that promote healthy, inclusive, and sustainable remote and hybrid work environments across diverse European contexts.

5. Project identity

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Project duration: 42 months (February 2024 – July 2027)

Website: <https://winwin4worklife.eu/>

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/winwin4worklife-eu-project>

Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=61556829871479>

Instagram: <https://www.instagram.com/winwin4worklife/>

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